

The Evolution of Language in the Age of Social Media: New Forms and Trends

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Abstract: the article deals with the role and importance of social media in the language of modern society, as well as the impact of their use on linguistic norms. Special attention is paid to the proliferation of abbreviations and acronyms, their impact on traditional rules of grammar and spelling, and the changing language standards under the influence of digital communications.

Keywords: norm, role, acronyms, media, social networks, content, communication.

Social media play a significant role in the change and development of language in modern society. They not only help people to communicate and share information, but also lead to new forms of expression and communication. In 2007, American researcher B. Solis in his article “Defining Social Media” gives several definitions of social media, one of which is of some interest to us: “Social media, in its most general form, is the way people discover, read, and comment on news, information, and content. It is a fusion of social and high technology that transforms monologue (one to many) into dialog (many to many)”.

In B. Mc Connell's book “Content Epidemic. Marketing in social networks and the blogosphere” suggests that social media should be understood as ‘a community of people expressing thoughts online, as well as those who interact with them’. The following definition was published by one of the social media researchers J. Thornleigh: “Social media is online communication in which the individual fluidly and flexibly changes his or her role, acting either as an audience or as an author. This is done using social software that allows anyone without specialized coding knowledge to post, comment, move, edit information and build communities around shared interests”¹. Social media are computer technologies that facilitate the creation and sharing of information, ideas, career interests, and other forms of expression through virtual communities and networks. The variety of stand-alone and embedded social media services available today presents problems of definition; however, there are some common features. There are many varieties of social communication media - business networks, dating sites, services, forums, online stores, various websites, and social networks.

One of the most prominent trends in social media is the use of abbreviations and acronyms. Internet communication is communication without boundaries. One of the most striking features of Internet communication is the use of a large number of abbreviations. This widespread use of abbreviations in virtual communication is explained by the economy of speech means. Users seek to simplify and speed up communication by creating short forms of words and phrases that have become popular around the world. Examples include English abbreviations such as “LOL” (laugh out loud) or “OMG” (Oh my God), “YW” (please), “ILY” (I love you). Russian-speaking users also abbreviate words, using, for example, “chel” (person), “ksta” (by the way), “ls” (personal message), “knch” (of course), etc. These changes are

helping to reduce time spent on correspondence, but they are also creating new language norms that can permeate spoken language and even professional settings.

Social media is an ideal platform for the emergence of new words and expressions. For example, the word “hype” has become part of everyday Russian and is used to describe the hype surrounding an event. Such words often originate in Internet cultures and memes, quickly spreading among users and then passing into everyday language. In addition, social platforms such as TikTok, Instagram and Twitter have contributed to the rapid popularization of words and expressions that were previously known only in narrow circles. For example, terms related to gaming communities, memes or trends have become clear even to those who are not active internet users.

On social media, people often break traditional grammatical rules. For example, users may intentionally write with a small letter or use non-standard abbreviations such as “sh” instead of “what” or “sha” instead of “now”. These changes help to express emotions or attitudes, making communication more informal and lively. Moreover, so-called “Internet languages” or “online dialects” are emerging. For example, the Russian language uses expressions such as “pzhlst” (please) or “sps” (thank you), which are perceived as informal and even rude in ordinary life, but have become commonplace in social networks.

Thanks to social media, many words and expressions cease to be “local” and become international. People from different countries interact and borrow words from each other, which contributes to the creation of a global linguistic space. English, in particular, has become a language that is actively used in social networks around the world, and therefore English-language words and phrases are actively penetrating into other languages. In Russian, for example, the words “like”, “post”, “storis”, “chat” and many others are actively used.

Social media influence not only everyday language, but also professional and academic communication styles. In science and business, for example, many concepts related to digital technologies first appeared in online discussions and then were integrated into professional jargon. Language used to be more regulated: people tried to write and speak “by the rules” and conform to literary standards. In social media, these rules are blurred and people feel freer to express themselves. As a result, the norm becomes more flexible, and the boundary between “right” and “wrong” language use becomes less clear.

Due to its popularity, social media provides an ever-increasing amount of linguistic data in different languages, produced by a huge number of participants. This makes it possible to trace interlingual relationships, to reach conclusions inductively and deductively, to generalize globally and locally. That is, to use the linguistic material in the most convenient and most relevant to the purpose of the study. The language of social media is extremely interesting from the point of view that individuals (users/potential customers) and brands interact very closely here. The field of research of linguistic transformations in the paradigm of communication in social media and their direct impact on the structural elements of language as such is one of the promising areas of linguistic research, as well as disciplines at the intersection of linguistics and related sciences. Scientists believe that differential linguistic analysis of social media is a unique method of unobtrusive, and therefore maximally reliable, comprehension of social and psychological characteristics of people's daily speech behavior.

Social media have had a powerful impact on language, transforming its form and content. These changes have made language more dynamic and adaptable to the demands of the digital age. On the one hand, this can lead to simplification and standardization of language, on the other hand, it contributes to its enrichment and the creation of new ways of expression.

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